

Flow Behaviour of Bentonite Suspension. Part-I. Interaction with Electrolytes

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Bihar bentonite, purified from non-clayey gritty matters, inorganic and organic compounds, was finally converted into mono-ionic sodium form. The purified clay was characterised by chemical analysis, CEC, DTA and X-ray for pure montmorillonitic nature. The suspension characteristics in terms of rheological behaviour were studied in presence of different electrolytes, such as LiCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂, BaCl₂, Al(NO₃)₃ and ZrOCl₂. The influence of electrolytes on the colloidal properties of the clay suspension was indicated by the determination of plastic viscosity and yield value through rotational cup and bob viscometer of McMichael type.

THE sensitivity of clay suspension towards addition of electrolytes is of paramount importance in drilling fluids, fabrication of ceramic wares by slip casting, application of unshaped refractories such as mortars, ramming masses and castables on the furnace wall before the commencement of relining. Adjustment of appropriate amount of electrolyte enables a ceramic technologist to control the suspensibility as well as the flow behaviour of clay suspension. The slip should possess low viscosity for easy flowing and high yield value (e.g. the minimum force required to start flow) for high green strength. Hence, the study of flow behaviour of bentonite became essential for the analysis of particle interaction.

According to Henry and Taylor¹, who studied the changes in pH and apparent viscosity of clay slips, the pH of exchange neutrality of each clay agreed closely with maximum in the pH-viscosity curve. Marshall² pointed out that the addition of increasing amounts of monovalent bases to electro-dialysed montmorillonite (bentonite) increased the viscosity. The viscosity attained a maximum just before the complete neutralisation and then experienced a second rise. The first maximum was less marked with K⁺ than Li⁺ or Na⁺. The second maximum showed a different order, i.e. K⁺ > Li⁺ > Na⁺.

Alader³ showed that only the external surfaces of the particles affected the stability of bentonite suspension whereas during the ion-exchange or hydration the inner portion of the particles also reacted. This observation explained the wide variation of mechanical properties of films produced from bentonite suspension. Sengupta and Indra⁴ observed that the viscosity and yield value curve of bentonite suspension at various stages of neutralisation plotted against the corresponding alkali passed through a maximum and then a minimum in the same way as the buffer capacity curve.

Olphen⁵ studied the effect of neutral salts, such as NaCl on the yield stress of 3% suspension of dialysed Na-Woming bentonite and concluded that the formation of structure in the pure gel can be attributed to edge-to-flat-surface association of the flat micelles caused by opposed charge of the double layer at the surfaces. Williams *et al.*⁶ showed that the variations in rheological properties of natural bentonites were affected greatly by the Na/Ca ratio⁴ by the weight dilution of the colloidal fraction by minerals, and by varying amounts of soluble salts. Marshall⁷ concluded that plasticity of kaolinite is a result of physical properties and that of montmorillonite a result of chemical properties. Other clay minerals are intermediate between kaolinite and montmorillonite depending upon the make up of the clay mineral.

The flocculation of Na-montmorillonite of five different particle sizes was studied by Kahn⁸ in presence of NaCl, CaCl₂, AlCl₃ and La(NO₃)₃. Flocculation value (concentration of electrolyte where sharp change of viscosity occurred) of NaCl was relatively independent of particle size of Na-montmorillonite concentration whereas the flocculation value of other electrolytes was strongly affected by ion-exchange. Gabrysh *et al.*⁹ studied the effects of concentration, temperature, suspension medium, hydrogen ion concentration and successive application of the shear stress on the flow behaviour of colloidal suspensions of bentonite. They concluded that at high shear rates all flow curves coincided and that temperature had no effect. Van Olphen¹⁰ showed that the addition of NaCl to the purified 2% Na-bentonite suspensions in water initially decreases the yield stress, but beyond about 5 meq dm⁻³ increases it. The same is true for the relative viscosities and the sediment volumes of more dilute suspensions. The sequence of flocculation-deflocculation-flocculation of the clean suspensions is explained by the concept of positive edge charge of the

clay plates, allowing positive edge of negative flat-surface flocculation. The change in viscosity of Wyoming bentonite was studied by Nash¹¹ with variations in cation ionisation, base saturation, clay concentration, NaCl concentration and type of exchangeable cation. The viscosity changes little with decreasing cation ionisation until a certain threshold value is reached. Below this value the viscosity increases rapidly, indicating that the repulsive potential barrier has been reduced to the order of the kinetic energy of the particles.

Previous workers measuring apparent viscosity, did not fully reveal the nature of suspension so far as the rheology is concerned. The properties of suspension characteristics as well as the stability of clay suspensions possess widespread practical application. Thus, the present work has been designed to study systematically the interactions of bentonite clay with different electrolytes at various concentrations.

Experimental

Bihar bentonite, greyish in colour and one of the best varieties of montmorillonite containing clays of India, was selected for the present investigation. The clay, after purifying from non-clay gritty material and associated organic and inorganic impurities, became white with slight yellowish tinge. The purified clay containing the maximum portion of 1 μ and below size fractions was always stored in a constant temperature incubator ($36 \pm 1^\circ$) to avoid any extraneous moisture absorption. For the present study, bentonite was converted into Na-form and its usual characteristics are furnished in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND OTHER CHARACTERISTICS OF BENTONITE IN Na-FORM

Constituents	% (w/w)	Cation exchange capacity meq/100 g	DTA peak temp.
SiO ₂	51.30		155,565 (endo)
Al ₂ O ₃	27.31		
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.41	97.20	940 (exo)
CaO	—		
MgO	1.36		
Loss on ignition	14.89		

AnalaR and E. Merck quality salts of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂, BaCl₂, Al(NO₃)₃ and ZrOCl₂ were used for the preparation of the solutions of electrolytes. In order to have the same milliequivalent of cations per ml of solution, electrolyte solutions containing mono-, di-, tri- and tetra-valent cations were prepared at 1, 0.5, 0.33 and 0.25 molar concentrations.

The suspensions were prepared at 10% concentration in a wide mouth glass stoppered reagent bottle of 250 ml capacity. A small volume of distilled water was added to make a slurry, followed by addition of required volume of the standard solution

of electrolyte. Finally, the volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The suspension was aged for overnight, shaken in a mechanical shaker for 3 h and then immediately used for measurement of viscosity.

The viscosity was measured in a modified McMichael viscometer utilising Reiner and Riwlin equation¹² for plastic flow in a rotational viscometer.

For yield value,

$$f = CT_a \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Plastic viscosity } (U) = \frac{(T - T_a)S}{\Omega} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } S = \frac{\frac{1}{R_b^2} - \frac{1}{R_c^2}}{4\pi h} \text{ and } C = \frac{S}{\ln R_c/R_b},$$

R_b, R_c = Radius of the bob and cup, respectively, U = 1/μ plastic viscosity, Ω = angular viscosity, h = depth of immersion of the bob, and T = movement due to external forces (torque).

Results

From the chemical analysis, cation-exchange capacity and differential thermal analyses nature of the montmorillonite in Bihar bentonite was ascertained. The chemical analysis indicates montmorillonite is dioctahedral with Al³⁺ in the octahedral sites. Some of these sites are substituted by Fe³⁺ and Mg²⁺. There were also substitution in the tetrahedral silica layer by Al³⁺.

The rheological characteristics (yield value and plastic viscosity) were determined from the multi-point consistency curves, by the plot of r.p.m. vs torque. The nature of the flow curve did not differ to a great extent. The flow curves of 10% Na-bentonite suspension in presence of BaCl₂, shown in Fig. 1, is representative. The relative change of plastic

Fig. 1. Flow curves of 10% Na-bentonite suspension in presence of barium chloride: (1) 0.5, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 3.0 and (5) 4.0 meq per 10 g Na-bentonite.

viscosity and yield value with addition of electrolytes are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 and the results are provided in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Plastic viscosity relationship of 10% Na-bentonite suspension during interaction with different electrolytes: (1) LiCl, (2) NaCl, (3) KCl, (4) MgCl₂, (5) CaCl₂, (6) BaCl₂, (7) Al(NO₃)₃, and (8) ZrOCl₂.

Discussion

The yield value figures reveal that the nature of the flow of 10% Na-bentonite suspension changed from Newtonian to non-Newtonian during interaction with electrolytes in all cases. Higher yield value was observed with CaCl₂ followed by LiCl, Al(NO₃)₃ and ZrOCl₂ with specified addition of electrolytes. At the initial point of addition (0.5 meq per 10 g clay) the order of the cations with

Fig. 3. Yield value relationship of 10% Na-bentonite suspension during interaction with different electrolytes: (1) LiCl, (2) NaCl, (3) KCl, (4) MgCl₂, (5) CaCl₂, (6) BaCl₂, (7) Al(NO₃)₃, and (8) ZrOCl₂.

respect to plastic viscosity and yield value may be written as: Al³⁺ > K⁺ > Mg²⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Zr⁴⁺ > Li⁺ > Ba²⁺ > Na⁺, and Ca²⁺ > Zr⁴⁺ > Li⁺ > K⁺ > Na⁺ > Mg²⁺ > Al³⁺ > Ba²⁺, respectively. In each case, with addition of electrolyte the plastic viscosity appreciably increased. Different cations did not produce a significant difference in plastic viscosity. This indicates the degree of interaction is approximately the same in this range. Still, Ca²⁺ and Al³⁺ showed relatively higher plastic viscosity throughout the whole range of addition. The nature of yield value curves are not identical. An upward trend followed by a decrease at the final point of addition was observed with Li⁺, Na⁺ and Al³⁺ whereas all other cations except Ba²⁺ showed continuous increase of yield value on gradual addition of electrolyte. The initial change of yield value was prominent with K⁺, Mg²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺. Thus the flow

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF GRADUAL ADDITION OF ELECTROLYTES ON FLOW BEHAVIOUR OF 10% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION

Electrolyte	Meq added per 10 g clay	Plastic viscosity poise $\times 10^3$	Yield value dyne cm^{-2}
LiCl	0.5	29.63	0.5971
	1	27.06	0.6348
	2	27.67	0.6552
	3	30.55	0.8600
NaCl	4	33.33	0.6961
	0.5	28.86	0.5323
	1	27.66	0.5393
	2	30.31	0.5459
KCl	3	30.58	0.5665
	4	31.77	0.5010
	0.5	33.90	0.5869
	1	24.05	0.3276
MgCl ₂	2	30.07	0.3344
	3	30.81	0.4915
	4	30.87	0.4640
	0.5	32.29	0.5222
CaCl ₂	1	26.25	0.4983
	2	26.86	0.3252
	3	27.52	0.5393
	4	27.86	0.5323
BaCl ₂	0.5	32.01	0.7780
	1	31.86	0.7303
	2	30.92	0.6961
	3	33.67	0.8600
Al(NO ₃) ₃	4	34.87	0.4915
	0.5	29.58	0.3685
	1	27.92	0.4094
	2	28.56	0.4164
ZrOCl ₂	3	28.86	0.4879
	4	28.87	0.4915
	0.5	33.92	0.4743
	1	32.55	0.4983
	2	30.09	0.5501
	3	31.41	0.6212
	4	33.67	0.4915
	0.5	31.54	0.6416
	1	30.20	0.4846
	2	28.87	0.4846
	3	28.41	0.5187
	4	32.77	0.4607

properties of the suspension may be satisfactorily controlled as per requirement by suitable addition of electrolyte and the curves will be very much helpful in predicting the rheology.

The decrease of yield value and plastic viscosity in presence of electrolytes may be explained by the fact that here both the double layers are compressed whereby effective charge is reduced. Under this condition, attraction is less than repulsion because both edge-to-face (EF) attraction and face-to-face (FF) repulsion are diminished and thus the particles are disengaged, breaking the cardhouse structure. The increase of plastic viscosity and yield value in presence of electrolytes may be explained by the fact that in presence of high concentration of low potential cations or low concentration of high potential cations both the double layers are compressed to a greater degree. Under this condition, the van der Waals attraction between edges and faces supplements the opposite charge attraction. The subtle balance between EF attraction and FF repulsion becomes favourable for the formation of cardhouse structure. Simultaneously EF association by van der Waals attraction is likely to occur, which may contribute to the resulting increase in yield value and plastic viscosity. At high salt concentration (4 meq per 10 g of clay) decrease of yield value may be due to rapid occurrence of FF association by which the number of particles in the cardhouse is reduced thereby decreasing the strength.

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